

GREAT Case Study GCS10

Beat The Heat

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List of Abbreviations

CA	Consortium Agreement
CO	Confidential
DIH	Digital Innovation Hub
DI	Digital Innovation
DMP	Data Management Plan
DoA	Description of Action
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EC	European Commission
EGE	The European Group on Ethics in Science and New Technologies
GREAT	Games Realising Effective and Affective Transformation
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
UKRI	United Kingdom Research & Innovation
WP	Work Package

1. Executive Summary

This report is an overview of the case study '*Beat the Heat*' (GCS10). '*Beat the Heat*' is the tenth case study in the EU Horizon-funded project *GREAT – Games Realising Effective and Affective Transformation* (<https://www.greatproject.gg/>). The case study centres around a co-designed serious game developed to be utilized as a facilitation tool between citizens and policy makers. Through learning and role-play scenarios, target groups were provided a platform to: voice their attitudes towards issues of heat in school environments as a lived experience; gain valuable insights into specific green infrastructure initiatives in an age appropriate way, aligned with existing educational policy.

'*Beat the Heat*' was implemented from February 2025 until February 2026 in Cyprus. The case study was led by an academic partner in the GREAT project, Frederick University and was sponsored by Unit of Education for the Environment and Sustainable Development (EESD) of the Cyprus Ministry of Education, Sport and Youth. The unit is responsible for monitoring the implementation and updating of the National Strategic Planning for Environmental Education with a focus on Sustainable Development, which is the foremost policy text of the Republic of Cyprus for the promotion of Education for the Environment and Sustainable Development, in formal and non-formal education.

The case study engaged policy makers, educators, teacher trainers, energy experts, and urban planners, in a participatory process on the topic of school communities face rising temperatures, heatwaves, and limited shaded or climate-responsive outdoor infrastructure. The focus of the case study is a co-designed serious game developed in collaboration with Serious Games Interactive (SGI) partner in the GREAT project.

A series of 3 face to face serious dilemma games took place during the case study including 42 participants. The game was split into two parts: In part 1 players answered questions related to their school environment, and actions regarding heat and rising temperatures; and during part 2 they engaged in short quiz exercises. Participants explored: Cooling Strategies; Energy use (especially focused on air-conditioning); Green Infrastructure and Alternative Solutions in particular relevance to their school communities. In-game data was collected via: participant voting and ranking; free text input; and word clouds. Game play was further evaluated through teachers' feedback and expert interviews.

Results show that climate adaptation becomes meaningful for younger learners when it is grounded in everyday school spaces. Across co-design workshops, educators and policy stakeholders consistently emphasised that abstract or global climate narratives are difficult for children to engage with. Focusing instead on schoolyards, shaded areas, and outdoor comfort provides a concrete and developmentally appropriate entry point into climate adaptation.

From a policy perspective, the contribution of '*Beat the Heat*' lies in establishing the conditions for future youth participation in climate adaptation discussions. Rather than positioning children as passive recipients of information, the game prepares a method for engaging them as contributors to conversations about school environments under the Whole School Approach. Findings suggest that serious games can be a powerful tool for consultation with youth. Conducted within the local context in

Cyprus ‘Beat the Heat’ demonstrate how serious games can support climate citizenship across age groups, from adult policy dialogue to youth engagement, while remaining grounded in real institutional and policy contexts.

2. Introduction

‘*Beat the Heat*’ (GCS10) is the tenth case study in the EU Horizon-funded project GREAT – Games Realising Effective and Affective Transformation (<https://www.greatproject.gg/>). The case study is situated within the framework of Cyprus’ national strategy for Education for Sustainable Development (ESD), which is being implemented through the Whole School Approach supported by the Ministry of Education, Sports and Youth. This policy emphasizes the integration of sustainability principles across school culture, operations, curriculum, and community engagement. The goal is to embed environmental stewardship not just in what is taught, but in how schools’ function and engage with their wider communities.

The case study is sponsored by the Unit of Education for Environment and Sustainable Development, a horizontal unit under the Ministry of Education, Sports and Youth, supports national ESD implementation through teacher training, resource development, and school-wide capacity building. While in Cyprus there is strong institutional support for sustainability, schools vary significantly in digital infrastructure and readiness for implementing game-based learning. Socially, the activity is taking place in a context where educators are increasingly aware of climate change but face challenges in translating systemic issues into student-friendly learning experiences. This setting created a valuable opportunity to prototype educational innovations, such as serious games, while grounding them in real policy frameworks.

The case study theme ‘Beat the Heat’ is based in Cyprus, where communities, and in the context of this research, school communities face rising temperatures, heatwaves, and limited shaded or climate-responsive outdoor infrastructure. Urban heat is an increasingly pressing challenge for cities worldwide, with rising temperatures intensifying risks to health, wellbeing, and everyday functioning (Tong et al, 2021). Children are among the groups most affected by extreme heat (Qian et al, 2025), particularly in school environments where outdoor spaces are often poorly adapted to warming climates (Antoniadis et al, 2020). Despite this, climate adaptation remains underrepresented in formal education, and when addressed, Climate change education is often presented in ways that remain distant from students’ everyday contexts, highlighting the need for pedagogical approaches that connect climate issues to learners’ lived experiences (Perwitasari, 2023).

Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) has long emphasised the importance of equipping learners with knowledge, skills, and values to engage with environmental change. However, much climate education continues to prioritise awareness and information provision, with limited attention to how children, can meaningfully engage with adaptation as a situated, spatial, and socially negotiated process (Reid, 2019). This gap is particularly evident in relation to urban heat, where adaptation strategies are closely linked to spatial design decisions, energy use, and everyday practices in specific urban settings such as schoolyards, streets, and neighbourhoods (Norton et al., 2015).

Recent research has highlighted the potential of serious games and participatory learning approaches to address complex sustainability challenges by creating spaces for exploration, negotiation, and imagination (Tan & Nurul-Asna, 2023). Dilemma-based learning engages learners with contested sustainability issues by foregrounding trade-offs and competing priorities rather than singular correct answers (Juhola et al, 2013). This case study builds on previous serious dilemma games developed under the GREAT project. Previous approaches towards Green Jobs, (Kieslinger, et al, 2025), Green Roofs (Merry, 2025), water sanctity (Watson, 2026) and the understanding of the UN sustainable goals through the ‘Prosper’ game (Griffiths et al, 2026), were largely applied in higher education, policy contexts, and adult citizen engagement, their adaptation for younger learners within formal school settings remain unexplored. Through both the previous GREAT project research and current literature, questions persist regarding: how dilemma-based games can be designed to be age-appropriate; how they can be embedded within existing educational structures; and how they might contribute to broader sustainability goals beyond individual learning (Asadzadeh et al, 2024).

The key objectives of this case study were to:

- 1. Adapt the GREAT/DiBL methodology for younger “citizens” (ages 10–12):**
To demonstrate that dilemma-based serious games can be designed in an age-appropriate way for primary school students, while still engaging them with real climate adaptation trade-offs (rather than simplified “right answers”).
- 2. Elicit and structure youth perspectives on a local climate dilemma (urban heat):**
To use gameplay and co-creative activities to help children express their lived experiences of heat and outdoor comfort, and translate these into structured, interpretable insights about cooling strategies in school environments.
- 3. Produce policy-relevant evidence aligned with the Whole School Approach:**
To generate outputs that can inform ESD and school-environment reform under Cyprus’ Whole School Approach, creating a pathway for student voice to connect with educators and policy stakeholders (e.g., EESD Unit / Ministry of Education and the Cyprus Energy Agency).

3. Methodology

‘Beat the Heat’ aimed to evaluate how effective are games-based activities in eliciting, representing and communicating citizens’ views on social dilemmas. More specifically it aimed to demonstrate that the games-based methodology effectively: engaged participants; fostered meaningful dialogue and collaboration; enhanced understanding of urban heat, particularly in the school environment, the potential for sustainability; and increased youth citizen participation in both educational and school infrastructure planning discussions. The overarching GREAT research questions addressed through GCS10 were:

- **RQ1.** To understand how games-based activities can be designed to provide a link between citizens and policy makers: Through educator engagement, beat the heat explored how students’

experiences and opinions might be expressed through game-based learning and shared upward to policy discussions.

- **RQ 1.4** How widely applicable are games-based activities in eliciting, representing and communicating citizens' views on policy dilemmas, and which variables need to be taken into consideration when adapting them to different contexts: Through the exploration of local constraints (age group access, policy reform timing).
- **RQ 2.3** What are the benefits and risks to citizens of using games-based activities to elicit, represent and communicate their views on policy dilemmas: Through the assessment of the implications of introducing game-based activities into formal learning systems.

The study employed a variety of mixed methods allowing the case study lead to employ both qualitative and quantitative methodologies to triangulate the research findings. Overall the Research Design was based upon the GREAT projects case study cycle (see detailed breakdown below). These methods included: collaborative online workshops; expert interviews; and participant gameplay and in game evaluation questions. The central data collection instrument was the serious dilemma game *'Beat the Heat'*, produced by project Partner Serious Games Interactive (SGI), Denmark.

Figure 1: Evaluation Questions

Within the *'Beat the Heat'* case study the DiBL approach was chosen based on three key factors:

- Multiplayer dilemma-based solution
- Quantitative & Qualitative Research Style
- Ability to promote Exploration & Discussion

In order to develop the game multiple meetings took place with the Unit of Education for Environment and Sustainable Development as well as the Cyprus Energy Agency in order to, describe the dilemma in sufficient detail; provide real world scenarios to create compelling situations for the participants in the game; decide on the interactions that occur during the game; determine how and provide resources about the dilemma (e.g. text descriptions, photos) such as those shown in figure 2.

Figure 2. Screenshots of 'Beat the Heat' – Cyprus Energy Agency Rooftop

The dilemma game design was co-created by the case study lead, and a member of the SGI technical team, who acted in a consulting role. All requirements had been gathered from the Unit of Education

for Environment and Sustainable Development as well as the Cyprus Energy Agency, and the case study lead and SGI then took responsibility for the design. For the DiBL game a minimum of 8 participants were necessary for an effective session to be delivered, with a maximum of 25 participants if conducted in a true classroom environment. The full game and facilitation guide are available at: <https://www.greatproject.gg/blog/toolkit-beat-the-heat>

Once piloted and refined, a series of 3 face to face serious dilemma games took place during the case study including 42 participants. The game was split into two parts: In part 1 players answered questions related to their school environment, and actions regarding heat and rising temperatures; and during part 2 they engaged in short quiz exercises. Participants explored: Cooling Strategies; Energy use (especially focused on air-conditioning); Green Infrastructure and Alternative Solutions in particular relevance to their school communities. Within the game itself data was collected via: participant voting and ranking; free text input; and word clouds. Game play was further evaluated through teachers' feedback and expert interviews.

3.2 Participant selection

Participant selection for the case study in Cyprus began through an existing relationship between Frederick University and the Unit of Education for Environment and Sustainable Development. The case study lead of Frederick University presented the GREAT project to the Unit of Education for Environment and Sustainable Development and discussed the innovative means that the project could achieve in relation to investigating the potential of digital games and gameplay to engage citizens to provide input into developing policy priorities on climate change. This setting created a valuable opportunity to prototype educational innovations, such as serious games, while grounding them in real policy frameworks. As a result, the Unit of Education for Environment and Sustainable Development identified the whole school approach to ESD as a policy dilemma to be explored through the GREAT methodology, focusing on cooling of school spaces in Cyprus.

Game sessions were promoted in sessions in December 2025 with the main sessions taking place in January 2026. The primary means was through personal communication with both Public and Private schools.

Overview of DiBL participants:

- Total Participants: 42 Participants
- Total Game Sessions: 3
- Age Range: 9 - 12 Years
- 24 Female/ 18 Male
- Game session length: -Part 1 40 mins/Part 2 40 mins – Maximum (Generally lasting 70 mins in total).

Expert interview participants included a representative of the Unit of Education for Environment and Sustainable Development and the Cyprus Energy Agency. Participants were selected due to their extensive knowledge in both current consultation measures and knowledge in Urban Cooling and ESD implementation within the Cypriot context.

3.3 Ethical Considerations

Before any data collection took place, ethical approval was obtained from the Cyprus National Ethics Agency. Prior to participating in any sessions, parents of the participating children were introduced to the GREAT project, confirming their voluntary participation. This process ensured that all participants were fully aware of the study's objectives and their rights. Data collection was carried out using participants' mobile devices, tablets, or laptops and in the school environment the computer labs of the participating schools. To maintain privacy and confidentiality, all collected data were anonymized, with no identifying information retained. This approach upheld ethical standards and safeguarded participant confidentiality throughout the study.

3.4 Mapping of RQ's to Case Study:

Table 1. Mapping of research questions to the case study

Revised research objectives and questions	<i>Simple formulation in terms of GREAT</i>	<i>Yes/No</i>
RQ1. To understand how games-based activities can be designed to provide a link between citizens and policy makers.		
RQ1.1 Which games-based activities can be used to elicit, represent and communicate citizens' views on social dilemmas?	<i>How can GREAT be achieved?</i>	<i>NO</i>
RQ1.2 How effective are games-based activities in eliciting, representing and communicating citizens' views on social dilemmas?	<i>Does GREAT do what we want it to do?</i>	<i>NO</i>
RQ1.3 How efficient is the use of games-based activities in eliciting, representing and communicating citizens' views on social dilemmas?	<i>How much work is it to use the GREAT approach?</i>	<i>NO</i>
RQ1.4 How widely applicable are games-based activities in eliciting, representing and communicating citizens' views on social dilemmas, and which variables need to be taken into consideration when adapting them to different contexts?	<i>How widely applicable is what we do?</i>	<i>YES</i>

RQ2. To understand the benefits and risks to citizens, policy stakeholders and policy makers, of using games-based activities as a link between citizens and policy makers.		
RQ2.1 What are the affordances of games in eliciting and representing citizens' views in relation to social dilemmas.	<i>What is it about GREAT that makes it good for gathering and representing opinions and attitudes?</i>	<i>NO</i>
RQ2.2 What are the benefits and risks to policy makers and policy stakeholders of using games-based activities to elicit, represent and communicate citizens' views on social dilemmas?	<i>What is good and bad about GREAT for policy stakeholders and policy makers?</i>	<i>NO</i>
RQ2.3 What are the benefits and risks to citizens of using games-based activities to elicit, represent and communicate their views on social dilemmas?	<i>What is good and bad about GREAT for citizens?</i>	<i>YES</i>

The '*Beat the Heat*' case study design followed the GREAT projects case study cycle as seen in figures 1 and 2. The project objectives and steps in the cycle determined the types of activities and participants to be involved in the co-design processes, i.e. citizens, domain experts, policy stakeholders and policymakers etc. The following section outlines the steps of the methodology in relation to the '*Beat the Heat*' case study.

Figure 3: GREAT Case Study Cycle (Stakeholder Engagement)

Figure 4: GREAT Case Study Cycle (Partners)

3.4.1 Detail the design process for the case study:

Table 2. Detailing the design process for the case study

Step of Case Study Cycle	Overview of the Cycle
Create and Prioritise Research Topics (Step 1)	<p>Objectives: Create and prioritise research topics/ What the case study will achieve and with who?</p> <p>Expected Outputs: -Identify current issue/s that the potential case study sponsor wants to explore that creates a policy dilemma in an authentic context. -Identify who would need to be involved to gather representative opinions (named groups or organisations).</p> <p>Stage 1 Activities: A one-hour, in-person planning meeting took place at the Cyprus Pedagogical Institute with representatives from the GREAT project and the Education Unit for the Environment and Sustainable Development (EESD), part of the Ministry of Education, Sports and Youth. The discussion aimed at aligning project objectives with national education priorities and confirming the case study sponsors commitment. Participants were introduced to the GREAT project, the DiBL platform, and the structure of the case study cycle. During Step 1 the following outcomes were achieved:</p> <p>Case study aim defined: To explore how learning scenarios and games can enhance pedagogical practices for teaching climate change and sustainable development, thus transferring knowledge to policy makers towards the whole school approach.</p> <p>Target audience selected: Grade 5 & 6 students (age 10–12) were identified as the most impactful group due to curriculum reform schedules and feasibility of classroom access.</p> <p>Policy integration clarified: The unit emphasized that insights from the case study could feed into national policy development for Education for Sustainable Development (ESD).</p> <p>Commitment secured: The unit agreed to support the study, seeing it as an opportunity to understand how innovative tools can support the work of teachers and the wider school community.</p>

	<p>Preliminary content themes proposed: The unit identified existing educational themes that could form the basis for the dilemma games, including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Natural Disasters • Energy Audits • Temperature Monitoring in Cyprus • Sustainable School Spaces <p>Furthermore, it was decided that in the following steps we should: proceed with the design of a dilemma game tailored to primary education using the thematic areas above, ensure alignment with the national curriculum and current reforms in primary education, involve teacher trainers in Stage 2 to co-design game components based on classroom relevance and feasibility.</p>
<p>Collaborate in Study Design (Step 2)</p>	<p>Objectives: Collaborate in study design/ Game activity concepts</p> <p>Expected Outputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Scenario to elicit required insight - Identify activities to be designed - Thematic content that is needed - Data to be gathered and pipeline - Timeframe for implementation <p>Step 2 took place in 2 parts.</p> <p>Part A was a structured focus group, through facilitated dialogue and sharing of ideas between the case study lead of Frederick University and 6 members of the Unit of Education for Environment and Sustainable Development took place. Throughout the discussion, participants were encouraged to reflect on how these games might align with the Whole School Approach to sustainability and what support teachers might need to implement them effectively. Several stakeholders, including NGOs and the Cyprus Energy Agency, were suggested as potential collaborators for development and piloting. Overall, the interactions were mainly collaborative problem-solving, openness to experimentation, and the discussion of local contextual knowledge that would directly inform stage 3 of the case study.</p> <p>Key Information Provided by Participants were:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Piloting Environment: Participants recommended that the serious game be tested in an informal educational setting, such as a summer camp, before attempting integration into the formal school year. This ensures more flexibility and reduces pressure on educators and students. • Game Format: The game should be modular, with shorter sessions (e.g., 10-minute segments) rather than a long, experience. This makes

	<p>it easier to integrate into existing class structures or extracurricular activities.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technology Preparedness: Schools may not have sufficient infrastructure to support the game. It was advised that the pilot be accompanied by pre-prepared hardware (laptops, tablets) rather than relying on school resources. • Stakeholder Involvement: Participants emphasized the need to involve additional stakeholders, such as the Cyprus Energy Agency, NGOs, and policy experts, in co-design and feedback processes. (Step 3 of the Cycle) • Content Adaptation: There was a strong call for age-appropriate content and inclusive design, considering the diverse needs of students and teachers, including those unfamiliar or uncomfortable with digital tools. <p>Part B was a collaborative discussion and idea showcase between the Frederick University, Case Study Lead, a representative of the Cyprus Energy Agency and a games developer from SGI (Great project partner). The discussion was collaborative and narrowed down further the focus of the DiBL game. This was also a strategic discussion to draw out ‘pockets’ of the green infrastructure topic to focus on. Key interactions during the discussion highlighted:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clarification of roles, especially the Cyprus Energy Agency’s contribution to reviewing materials and ensuring alignment with policy goals and factual correctness. • Idea development for game format: The idea of using thermal images (e.g., from the rooftop project) as visual tools to prompt students to identify hot/cool areas was promoted. Once the game format was identified, gamification ideas were discussed. Small dilemmas were introduced, first it was decided that the game should introduce small dilemmas such as “You want to play outside but it’s too hot, what would you do?” Following this the game play could encourage students to vote on best solutions, or earn points for innovative suggestions (pending further testing). This raised questions of how this could be done technically. Finally, drawing inspiration from the Cyprus Energy Agency’s giant Jenga game which they currently use to go to schools and interact with school children (usually high school), it was suggested that there should be a link to physical activity (eg. Go outside and explore) with thematic questions (answered through the DiBL in a fun and engaging way).
<p>Collaborate in Design of Games-Based Activities (Step 3)</p>	<p>Objectives: Collaborate in game design</p> <p>Expected Outputs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Collaborative design of game activities - Co-create story and narrative and/or quiz game - Specify the detail of the dilemma scenario and/or quiz game

- Design interactions and deployment of content

Stage 3 of the case study cycle examined how a GREAT case study facilitator could take on a consulting role in the creation of a DiBL game, i.e. that the sponsors provide input, but the facilitation team completes the hands-on design work. Stage 3 also took place in 2 stages. The aim of step 3 was to:

- co-develop game content and learning prompts with key stakeholders (e.g. Cyprus Energy Agency, urban planners, teachers and the case study sponsor) that reflect locally relevant experiences of urban heat and climate adaptation.
- develop the game structure and scenario flow (started in step 2b) for use with children aged 10–12 in schools in Cyprus.
- ensure that the dilemmas, interventions, and visual elements (e.g. photos, maps, thermal images) are pedagogically appropriate and grounded in lived experience and expert knowledge.
- advance the readiness of the case study for school-based implementation

Stage 3a was a follow-up co-creation meeting involving collaborative dialogue between the case study lead of Frederick University, games designer of SGI (project partner) and a representative of the Cyprus Energy Agency in order to plan the upcoming DiBL game. Discussions were focused on the structure of the activity, the integration of data and visualizations into the DiBL tool, and how to effectively localize game content.

The selection of visual materials, included thermal and aerial imagery, to help students better understand spatial and environmental dynamics as well as temperature related data and energy comparisons. Based on the feedback from the Cyprus energy agency and the data and visual material gathered following the meeting, a first version of 'Beat the Heat was produced by project partner SGI.

Stage 3b was a further co-creation and testing session (of the initial version) involving the case study lead of Frederick University, and Serious Games Interactives, game designer, together with 5 representatives from the Unit of Education for the Environment and Sustainable Development (EESD) of the Cyprus Ministry of Education, including teacher trainers and educators.

Participants interacted directly with the digital game via the DiBL platform (<https://web.dibl.eu/caseview/8160?autostart> (Beat the Heat Playable Link), experiencing it from the perspective of both teachers and students. Discussions centered on the educational flow, age suitability, and classroom implementation of the game. Stakeholders provided practical and pedagogical feedback, including how to simplify technical content, clarify instructions, and ensure

	<p>visual materials were age-appropriate and locally relevant. Additional emphasis was placed on ensuring the game could align with the national ESD curriculum and be used as a tool to support teachers' reflective practice.</p> <p>Participants collaboratively identified improvements to the energy literacy and visual communication sections, refining examples and ensuring cultural sensitivity. The session confirmed the game's strong potential as a participatory learning tool linking students' lived experiences of heat with policy-relevant insights for educational reform in Cyprus.</p>
<p>Piloting and Gathering Data (Step 4)</p>	<p>Objectives: Piloting and Gathering Data</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Games activities with case study participants - Dilemma games with chosen focus group participants <p>Stage 4 Activities: During stage 4, a fully playable DiBL Dilemma game was produced and tested. The activity focused on the sessions of the dilemma game built in DiBL through steps 1-3. It consisted of a dialogue between the pilot facilitator (who had developed a good understanding of the dilemma and the objectives of the sponsor, and also had a good understanding of the DiBL platform) and the invited participants.</p> <p>The activity utilised the following steps prior to the sessions:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Invite participants through Frederick University Contacts 2. Set a date and Time for the pilot sessions <p>The activity utilised the following steps:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Introduce the facilitator 2. Set up the DiBL game through participants devices 3. Play part 1 of the game 4. Arrange snack and beverages for participants 5. Play part 2 of the game 6. Include short feedback questions <p>In total a series of 3 face to face serious dilemma games took place during the case study including 42 participants. The game was played in two parts: In part 1 players answered questions related to their school environment, and actions regarding heat and rising temperatures; and during part 2 they engaged in short quiz exercises. In both instances participants are asked to: engage in discussions to determine their key priorities and concerns. Within the game itself data was collected via: participant voting and ranking; free text input; and word clouds.</p>

	<p>Post-game 3 evaluation questions were asked to providing data to support the in-game data.</p>
<p>Data Interpretation and Outcomes (Step 5)</p>	<p>Objectives: Data interpretation and outcomes</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Collaborative data analysis - Interpretation of the data obtained from games activities - Assessment of the value of the data and possible need for further data collection <p>Stage 5 Activities: Following the pilot sessions, data generated through the DiBL platform and facilitator observations were reviewed and interpreted collaboratively by the case study team and project partners. The analysis focused on identifying patterns within participant responses, particularly in relation to learning outcomes, participant engagement, and perspectives on climate adaptation strategies in school environments.</p> <p>Data sources included in-game responses (multiple choice, free text inputs, and voting results), participant evaluation questions, facilitator notes, and feedback from education stakeholders including the Cyprus Energy Agency and the Unit for Education for the Environment and Sustainable Development (EESD). Particular attention was given to responses collected through pre- and post-reflection questions, which allowed comparison of participants’ initial ideas about coping with heat and their final suggestions for improving school environments.</p> <p>Interpretation of the data indicated that many participants shifted from initially suggesting individual or short-term cooling solutions (such as air conditioning or fans) toward nature-based or design-oriented strategies, including planting trees, increasing shade, and adding vegetation or roof gardens. This suggests that the gameplay experience supported reflection on alternative climate adaptation approaches.</p> <p>The evaluation data also demonstrated high levels of participant engagement and positive perceptions of the game format. Teacher observations and stakeholder feedback further reinforced these findings, highlighting the value of the dilemma-based structure for encouraging discussion and critical thinking.</p> <p>While the pilot provided valuable insights into the learning process and participant engagement, the analysis also identified areas where further data collection would strengthen understanding of the methodology, particularly through additional sessions across different schools and longer-term evaluation of learning outcomes.</p>
<p>Conclusions and Outputs (Step 6)</p>	<p>Objectives: Conclusions and outputs</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Policy conclusions & evaluation

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Collaborative formulation of case-study conclusions - Evaluation of the effectiveness of the method <p>Stage 6 Activities: The final stage of the case study within the time constraints of the GREAT project involved synthesising the results of the pilot implementation and reflecting collaboratively on the implications of the findings for both policy and methodology within the GREAT project.</p> <p>The conclusions of the Beat the Heat case study indicate that dilemma-based serious games can provide an effective method for engaging younger learners in discussions about climate adaptation and environmental decision-making. The combination of interactive gameplay, facilitated discussion, and place-based learning allowed participants to connect their everyday experiences of heat with broader sustainability challenges and potential solutions.</p> <p>From a policy perspective, the case study highlights the potential value of participatory educational tools in supporting the objectives of Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) and the Whole School Approach to sustainability promoted within the Cyprus education system. By providing structured opportunities for students to express ideas about improving their school environments, the methodology also demonstrates how youth perspectives can contribute to discussions around sustainable school design and climate resilience.</p> <p>The case study further contributes to the GREAT methodology by demonstrating how the DiBL approach can be adapted for younger participants within formal education contexts, expanding its application beyond adult citizen engagement. While further implementation and evaluation would be required to assess scalability and long-term impact, the pilot suggests that game-based participatory methods offer a promising pathway for connecting climate education, citizen engagement, and policy dialogue.</p>
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4. SWOT Analysis of Case Study Methodology:

Table 3. SWOT analysis of the case study methodology

<p>Strengths</p> <p><i>Examine the strengths of the case study methodology, such as the use of innovative data collection techniques (e.g., game-based activities, surveys) or high participant engagement levels.</i></p>	<p>Weaknesses</p> <p><i>Identify any methodological limitations encountered, such as sample size constraints or challenges in capturing a full range of participant perspectives.</i></p>
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Policy Stakeholder Collaboration:

- The EESD unit provided a real-world dilemma for implementation
- The case study included an organisation which had a clear point of view for a policy dilemma and whom were engaged in the co-development of the game

Further Stakeholder Engagement: Participation of further policy stakeholders (Cyprus Energy Agency and local schools and teachers) in the development and implementation

Innovative Games Based Data Collection Methodology: There was a variety of input methods in the DiBL approach: Free Text/Multiple Choice/Word Clouds/ Hierarchy/ Voting

Method of Delivery: The face to face nature of the game play allowed for the facilitator to not merely run the session but to provide further explanations when required

Structured yet Flexible Problem-Solving: The methodology combined real world scenarios which were relatable for the age group of the participants, allowing for realistic understanding discussions.

Bridging Gaps: Beat the Heat provided a novel platform for communication between youth citizens and policymakers.

Educational Value: The game facilitated learning by making complex urban sustainability issues (heat and energy) more accessible and engaging.

Alignment with Existing Policy Frameworks: The case study was aligned with Cyprus' Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) policy and the Whole School Approach, increasing its relevance for teachers and education stakeholders. Collaboration with the EESD Unit ensured that the activity reflected existing national

Permissions: Conducting research with school-aged participants required institutional permissions and ethical approval processes, including coordination with school leadership and relevant educational authorities. These procedures, while essential for safeguarding participants, introduced additional administrative steps and extended the preparation timeline prior to classroom implementation

Preparation and Resource Intensity: The case study preparation required significant preparation, facilitator training and structured materials and resources. This resulted in time delays to the initial case study timeline.

Participant Knowledge Gaps: The varied prior knowledge on the knowledge of sustainability, climate change, and energy affected the depth understanding and discussion in some instances, with participants relying on the facilitator to answer specialised questions on the subject. Due to the age group of participants (10-12), explanations were required to be age appropriate and in age appropriate context.

Participant Diversity: Participants engaged in the game sessions through school-based participation, which may have limited the diversity of participants involved. As such, some groups may have been underrepresented, including students from different socio-economic backgrounds or schools with limited access to digital resources.

Time Constraints and Pressure: Conducting the sessions within a tight time period after the Christmas break, which limited flexibility for scheduling additional sessions or repeating activities. Furthermore, the classroom time available for the activity (two teaching periods) constrained the depth of discussion and reflection that could be facilitated during gameplay.

<p>policy priorities and could potentially be integrated into educational practice.</p> <p>Age-Appropriate Adaptation of the GREAT Methodology: The Beat the Heat case study successfully adapted the DiBL approach, which has traditionally been used with adult participants, to a primary school audience (ages 10–12). Game design elements (visual prompts, simplified dilemmas, and co-creative activities) were tailored to ensure accessibility while maintaining engagement with complex sustainability issues.</p> <p>Place-Based and Experiential Learning: The game connected climate adaptation concepts to students’ everyday experiences of heat within their school environment, enhancing relevance and engagement. Activities encouraged students to observe and reflect on their physical surroundings, supporting spatial and environmental awareness.</p> <p>Youth Voice and Civic Engagement: The methodology created a structured opportunity for young participants to articulate their ideas and preferences regarding climate adaptation in school environments. This supports the GREAT project objective of amplifying citizen perspectives, extending it to younger age groups.</p>	<p>Technological Limitations: During game play ‘bugs’ in the game meant that some players could not answer specific questions, some were ‘thrown out’ of the game and in one instance participants could not answer correctly as they had a frozen screen. In another the visual exercises were not possible on the PC format These technical hitches could have misconstrued the final answers of some participants.</p> <p>Long-Term Impact: Further research is required to examine the long-term impact.</p> <p>Limited Scale of Implementation: The pilot phase involved a relatively small number of sessions and participants, which limits the ability to generalise findings across broader educational contexts. Further implementation across additional schools would strengthen the evidence base.</p> <p>Curriculum Integration Constraints: Although the activity aligns with sustainability education objectives, integrating game-based learning within existing school timetables may present challenges for teachers due to curriculum time limitations and competing teaching priorities.</p>
<p>Opportunities</p> <p><i>Highlight areas for potential development, such as refining the methodology, expanding participant demographics, or exploring future research collaborations to enhance insights.</i></p>	<p>Threats</p> <p><i>Identify external challenges that may impact the study’s success, such as resource limitations, data access issues, or potential resistance from stakeholders.</i></p>
<p>Wider Policy Applications: The methodology can be adapted for other climate change challenges, such as waste management, or mobility.</p> <p>Public Engagement Expansion: The game could be used in broader community consultations and participatory policy development beyond urban heat.</p>	<p>Curriculum and Time Constraints in Schools: School timetables and curriculum requirements may limit the ability of teachers to incorporate additional activities such as serious games, particularly when instructional time is tightly structured around existing learning objectives.</p> <p>Limited Digital Infrastructure in Some Schools: As highlighted by the case study stakeholders, differences in digital infrastructure, device</p>

Scaling to Additional Schools and Educational

Contexts: The Beat the Heat methodology demonstrates potential for implementation across additional schools in Cyprus and other European contexts. With further refinement of the facilitator guide and supporting materials, the game could be integrated into a wider range of classrooms and educational settings.

Integration into Education for Sustainable

Development (ESD): The case study aligns strongly with the Whole School Approach to sustainability education promoted by the Cyprus Ministry of Education. This creates opportunities for the activity to be incorporated into ESD teaching practices and used as an additional educational resource for teachers.

Strengthening Youth Participation in Climate

Adaptation: The methodology provides a structured platform for amplifying youth perspectives on climate adaptation and school environments. Insights generated through gameplay could inform discussions on school design, energy use, and outdoor comfort, contributing to broader policy conversations around sustainable school environments.

Methodological Development within the

GREAT Project: Beat the Heat extends the GREAT methodology by demonstrating how DiBL approaches can be adapted for younger learners. This creates opportunities to further develop the approach for different age groups, educational contexts, and sustainability challenges.

Development of Future Research and

Educational Initiatives: The case study provides a foundation for future research projects and collaborations, including further exploration of serious games in sustainability education, participatory climate learning, and youth engagement in environmental decision-making.

availability, and internet connectivity across schools may affect the feasibility of implementing the DiBL platform consistently in all educational contexts.

Policy and Institutional Changes: Changes in education policy priorities, school leadership, or institutional support could influence the willingness of schools or education authorities to adopt new methodologies such as dilemma-based learning games.

Teacher Capacity and Training Needs:

Successful implementation of the activity relies on facilitation and understanding of the methodology. Without sufficient teacher training or support materials, the method may be difficult to replicate consistently across different classrooms.

5. Key Findings

Participant Engagement and Acceptability: Across the pilot implementation, 42 participants completed the Beat the Heat game activities, with 22 participants completing the post-game evaluation questions. Evaluation results indicate strong engagement with the game-based learning format. For the statement “I found the game enjoyable to play”, 95% of participants reported a positive response (59% strongly agreed and 36% agreed). Similarly, 82% of participants expressed interest in playing a similar game again during future lessons, suggesting that the game format was both engaging and perceived as valuable within the classroom setting. These results indicate that dilemma-based gameplay can function as a motivating and acceptable learning approach for younger participants.

Learning and Awareness of Cooling Strategies: Responses to in-game reflection questions suggest that many participants developed new awareness of passive cooling strategies and climate adaptation practices. At the beginning of the activity, many responses focused primarily on active cooling solutions, such as air conditioning, fans, or cold drinks. By the end of the game, responses more frequently referenced nature-based and design-oriented solutions, including planting trees, increasing shade, adding vegetation, and creating roof gardens. This shift suggests that gameplay supported participants in recognising alternative approaches to cooling school environments beyond mechanical systems.

Youth Perspectives on School Climate Adaptation: The gameplay created a structured opportunity for students to articulate ideas about how their school environments could become more comfortable during hot weather. Participants suggested a range of interventions, including planting trees, adding shaded areas, introducing roof gardens, installing additional vegetation, and reducing reliance on air conditioning. These responses demonstrate how the methodology can help translate everyday experiences of heat into concrete adaptation proposals, illustrating the potential of game-based approaches to capture youth perspectives on environmental design and climate adaptation.

Participation, Discussion, and Expression of Ideas: Facilitator observations and teacher feedback indicate that students engaged actively in discussion and decision-making during gameplay. The observing teacher noted that students demonstrated confidence in expressing their opinions and debating possible solutions, including proposing creative pathways for influencing school decision-making processes. This suggests that the activity supported the development of participatory skills, such as discussion, negotiation, and collaborative reasoning.

Stakeholder Feedback and Policy Relevance: Feedback from education stakeholders, including representatives from the Unit for Education for the Environment and Sustainable Development (EESD) and the Cyprus Energy Agency, highlighted the value of the dilemma-based approach in supporting critical thinking and informed decision-making. Stakeholders emphasised that the methodology could contribute to sustainability citizenship, encouraging students to reflect on environmental choices and the

implications of climate adaptation decisions within their communities. The case study therefore demonstrates how serious games can function as mediating tools connecting educational practice with broader sustainability policy discussions.

6. Data Gaps

The implementation of ‘Beat the Heat’ involved a relatively small number of participants (**42 total game completions, with 22 post-game evaluations**). While the results provide useful insights into participant engagement and learning processes, the sample size limits the ability to generalise findings across broader educational contexts. The evaluation focused primarily on **immediate participant responses and reflections during or directly after gameplay**. As a result, the available data does not provide insight into the **long-term impact of the activity**, such as sustained learning outcomes, behavioural change, or influence on school-level environmental practices. Some open-ended responses from participants were brief, humorous, or incomplete, which is expected given the **young age group (10–12 years)** involved in the study. While these responses still provide valuable qualitative insight into engagement and understanding, they sometimes limited the depth of analysis possible from the free-text data. Although the game included reflective questions before and after gameplay, the study did not include a **formal control group or comparative baseline dataset due to the nature of the participants**. As a result, changes in participant understanding cannot be measured through a controlled experimental design, but are instead interpreted through observed shifts in responses and participant reflections.

7. Policy Implications and Recommendations

The Beat the Heat case study demonstrates that dilemma-based serious games can provide an effective method for engaging young learners with climate adaptation issues in ways that are both accessible and meaningful. Feedback from the ESSD unit consider incorporating participatory and game-based learning approaches within sustainability education frameworks, particularly as part of the Whole School Approach to Education for Sustainable Development.

Supporting Youth Perspectives in Climate Adaptation Discussions: The DiBL approach provided a structured platform for students to express ideas about improving the thermal comfort and environmental quality of their school environments. These insights suggest that young people can contribute valuable perspectives on local climate adaptation challenges when provided with appropriate tools. Policymakers and education authorities may therefore benefit from exploring ways to incorporate youth perspectives into discussions on school infrastructure, outdoor learning environments, and sustainability initiatives.

Strengthening Links Between Education and Sustainability Policy: The collaboration between the GREAT project, the Cyprus Energy Agency, and the Unit for Education for the Environment and Sustainable Development highlights the value of cross-sector collaboration in developing educational tools that reflect real policy priorities. Future initiatives could further strengthen these links by creating structured mechanisms for translating classroom insights into policy-relevant discussions on school environments and climate resilience.

Teacher Support and Training: Successful implementation of game-based methodologies requires adequate support for educators. Policymakers should consider providing guidance materials, facilitator training, and adaptable teaching resources to help teachers integrate participatory climate learning activities within existing curricula.

Future Development and Scaling: The case study suggests that the Beat the Heat methodology could be replicated across additional schools and adapted for other sustainability topics, such as biodiversity, water use, or energy efficiency. Further research and pilot implementations would help evaluate the method at larger scales and explore its potential contribution to sustainability education initiatives across Europe.

8. Conclusion

The Beat the Heat case study demonstrates the potential of dilemma-based serious games to engage younger learners in discussions around climate adaptation and sustainability within school environments. Through the combination of interactive gameplay, facilitated discussion, and co-creative activities, the case study enabled students to connect their everyday experiences of heat with broader environmental challenges and potential adaptation strategies. Participant responses and teacher feedback indicate that the activity was both engaging and educationally valuable, supporting awareness of passive cooling strategies and encouraging students to articulate ideas for improving the comfort and sustainability of their school environments.

A key contribution of the case study lies in the adaptation of the GREAT dilemma-based learning (DiBL) methodology for a younger audience. While previous applications of the methodology within the GREAT project have largely focused on adult participants or higher education contexts, Beat the Heat demonstrates that the approach can be successfully tailored for primary school students when supported by age-appropriate design elements, visual prompts, and facilitated discussion. This extends the methodological scope of the GREAT project by illustrating how serious games can be applied within formal education settings while maintaining their participatory and deliberative characteristics.

The case study also highlights the value of collaboration between education stakeholders, policy actors, and game developers in designing learning tools that are both pedagogically relevant and aligned with policy priorities. Engagement with the Unit for Education for the Environment and Sustainable Development and the Cyprus Energy Agency helped ensure that the content of the game reflected real-world sustainability challenges and educational frameworks in Cyprus.

Overall, the findings suggest that dilemma-based serious games can function as mediating tools between education, citizen engagement, and sustainability policy, providing structured opportunities for young learners to explore complex environmental issues and express their perspectives. While further research would be required to assess long-term educational impact and scalability, the Beat the Heat case study provides valuable insights into how participatory game-based methods can support climate adaptation learning and contribute to broader sustainability education initiatives.

Referring back to the GREAT project's research questions, the Beat the Heat case study provides several insights into the role of game-based activities in connecting citizens with policy discussions. In relation to RQ1, the study explored how game-based learning activities can create a link between citizens and policymakers. Through collaboration with educators and policy stakeholders, the activity demonstrated how students' experiences and ideas regarding heat and school environments can be expressed through structured gameplay and discussion, creating potential pathways for these perspectives to inform broader policy conversations.

Regarding RQ1.4, the case study contributes insights into the applicability of game-based activities in eliciting and communicating citizens' views on policy dilemmas. The implementation highlighted several contextual variables that influence the adaptation of such activities, including the age of participants, educational settings, access to digital tools, and alignment with existing policy frameworks and curricula.

Finally, in relation to RQ2.3, the case study provides insight into both the benefits and potential risks of using games-based activities to elicit and communicate citizen perspectives. The findings suggest that such methods can support engagement, reflection, and discussion among participants, while also highlighting considerations related to facilitation, technological reliability, and integration within formal learning systems.

Overall, the Beat the Heat case study illustrates the potential of dilemma-based serious games to bridge education, citizen engagement, and sustainability policy, highlighting how participatory learning approaches can contribute to more inclusive and informed climate adaptation discussions.

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